

THE PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF “CONSTITUENT PEOPLES” IN THE LEGAL-POLITICAL FRAMEWORK OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA – A REVIEW THREE DECADES AFTER DAYTON

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Abstract

In 2025, the thirtieth anniversary of the signing of the Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA) will be marked. The agreement represented a minimal compromise between the three ethnic groups (Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats) for joint statehood. All the institutions that were established by it were, to a large extent, created by the overly primordial understanding of ethnicity institutionalized in the system through the introduction of the constitutional concept of “constituent peoples”. The science of comparative constitutional law is not overly preoccupied with this concept, for the simple reason that in established Western democracies, as well as other countries around the world, one nation or people has always been dominant by definition. The phrase “constituent peoples” in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) is not used in the sense of people (*populous*) as a collection of all citizens who are in a civil relationship with the country and who constitute its political people. Still, it is used in the sense of a separate ethnic identity. With this, the Constitution of BiH created a presumption of strong discrimination against non-constituent peoples (others, citizens) despite its formal provisions on non-discrimination. The issue of “constituent peoples” in BiH arises as problematic not only in the domain of human rights and fundamental freedoms but also in terms of the organization and structure of government. Hence, the purpose of this paper is to examine the repercussions caused by the introduction of the concept of “constituent peoples” into the entire post-Dayton political system of BiH. The basic thesis is that the idea of “constituent peoples” created an institutional framework for building a ‘negative’ peace through initial segregation and mutual control between the three ethnic groups, which over time failed to encourage their gradual integration and the building of democratic institutions, which were supposed to consolidate peace and pave the way for European integration. Therefore, the calls for the necessary “correction” of this concept, towards creating a civic and liberal counterbalance, to prevent the system from degenerating into a full ethnic democracy, are understandable. Hence, the idea of a more comprehensive constitutional reform, which would be best implemented within the framework of the country’s European integration path. With such a “Brussels Avenue”, BiH would gain the foundation that EU member states have today, which is characterized by internal integration and the development of institutions synonymous with a functional state. In this way, the shortcomings of the DPA would be corrected, and the integration process itself, along with the implementation of a clearly defined reform agenda, would be its positive upgrade.

Keywords: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Dayton Peace Agreement, constituent peoples, consociational democracy, ethnocracy;

1 INTRODUCTION

In 2025, Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) will mark the thirtieth anniversary of the signing of the Dayton Peace Agreement (DPA). The Agreement, which has been in force for three decades (almost an entire generation of this country grew up under it), was reached “at Wright-Patterson Air Base in Dayton, Ohio (...) and later signed in an official ceremony on 14 December 1995 in Paris” (Vomlela, 2017: 28). Thirty years later is the right moment not only to summarize the achievements but also to reflect on the challenges that BiH faces today.

Not even three decades after its signing, the academic community that deals with and studies the legal and political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is without analogy and precedent in the comparative science of contemporary political systems, has left the impression that the Agreement did not create a presumption for a modern, civil state as part of the family of European nations. On the contrary, the unfolding of the Bosnian crisis continued to be a European conundrum in which many minds tested their diplomatic skills, and many armies the correctness of their struggle for reassurance (Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 12). Some authors, such as Maršić and Marko (2007: 1), go even a step further by revising Carl von Clausewitz’s famous thought about the post-Dayton political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which created the assumption of “the continuation of the war but by other means”. Scarred by the bloody war in the 1990s, following the breakup of Yugoslavia, the Peace Agreement was intended to mediate and strike a delicate balance between the country’s three main ethnic groups – Bosniaks, Serbs and Croats – by granting them special rights and additional influence (Nurkić & Isanović, 2023: 2). Dayton allowed for “a minimum compromise between the different ethnic groups on common statehood” (Rasidović, 2022: 2). During this period, new models of federalism (Belgium, Russia, Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Iraq) and territorial autonomy (Spain and Italy) were adopted (Keil, 2014: 80).

The International Community, which brokered the Agreement, remained ambiguous about the integrity of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This created assumptions for different political interpretations of the DPA, especially its substantive implementation, which remained a contentious issue. Primarily, this was due to the following dilemma – whether the Agreement is a compromise whose next step should be the division of the country along ethnic lines; or whether it should be the first step towards stopping this scenario and starting a gradual peaceful reintegration of the country (Bianchini, 2016: 135). But, except for the Vance-Owen plan³³ (1993), such ambiguity was offered by all previous plans for overcoming the Bosnian crisis, such as the Cutileiro’s mediation³⁴ (March 1992), the Owen-Stoltenberg plan,³⁵ the Washington Agreement (March 1994),³⁶

³³ „The plan envisioned the establishment of ten provinces based on geographical, economic, and other criteria, with the names of the provinces not referring to ethnic characteristics“ (Efendić, 2018: 66). However, one of the three peoples would dominate them, but this was not recognized as a constitutive category (Nešković, 2017: 196).

³⁴ It envisaged a political federation based on ethnic nations but without compact territories (Nešković, 2017: 190, 193). The Bosniaks rejected it due to their strong opposition to regions based on an ethnic principle (Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 17).

³⁵ This plan revived the idea of three separate states under one confederal state, and rewarded Serbian and Croatian aspirations; therefore, it is logical that Bosniaks were not thrilled with it

and the Contact Group plan (1994),³⁷ which instead of stopping the war inspired new cycles of violence (Ćurak, 2015: 45).

2 THE HISTORICAL GENESIS OF THE BOSNIAN-HERZEGOVINIAN STATE AND THE ETHNO-RELIGIOUS DIMENSION OF BIH

According to Malcolm (1995: 13), there is no doubt that Bosnia and Herzegovina “is a country that has its own historical identity – in fact, it is one of the historic countries in Europe, with an almost uninterrupted history as a distinct geopolitical entity from the Middle Ages to the present day. For most of the period from 1180 to 1463 it was an independent kingdom; from 1580 to 1878 it was an *eyalet* (a term denoting the largest territorial unit in the Ottoman Empire); from 1878 to 1918 a ‘crown land’ within Austria-Hungary; and from 1945 to 1992 a federal republic”. However, another group of authors, such as Sarajlić (2010: 2), believes that one thing is BiH as a country that was at the crossroads of numerous conquests and wars of great empires, both European and Asian, and quite another is its statehood (1943) and independence (1992), which were relatively short-lived. Marković is on the same line of thinking. According to him: “The Medieval Bosnian state cannot be taken as a raw-model, as it was not a modern, but rather a feudal state. Later, with the arrival of the Turks and the Austro-Hungarians, Bosnia and Herzegovina became an administrative area, organized, until the late 19th century, as part of a pre-modern state” (Marković, 2015: 108). It is worth highlighting here the opinion of the Croatian political scientist with origin from Bosnia and Herzegovina, Mirjana Kasapović (2005), who claims that for centuries Serbs, Bosniaks/Muslims, and Croats have never jointly, permanently, and *en masse* advocated for a common state, and have only coexisted together thanks to the authoritarianism of the regimes (the Ottoman Empire, the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, and the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, later the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia).

Regarding the three ethnic identifications that exist in Bosnia and Herzegovina, it is essential to note that their ethnic and national consciousness, in a political sense, is specific compared to other European experiences, as religious division and affiliation will, over time, become a marker of national identification (Mesić, 2006: 291). The 14th and 15th centuries were crucial for the development of religious divisions, as the Ottoman conquest of the Balkans and Medieval Bosnia led to a significant portion of the local population adopting Islam as their religion, thereby creating the recognizable religious triangle in Bosnia and Herzegovina that exists today (Radušić, 2009: 3). “Since the beginning of the 16th century Bosnian-Herzegovinian society had a tendency towards the creation of a multi-religious, and multi-national society” (Katz, 2017: 202). The subsequent demographic development of all three religious groups took place in such a way that no later nation had, nor would have, an absolute majority, which contributed to the complication of interethnic relations (Radušić, 2009: 3).

(Dašić & Nedeljković, 2016: 22-23). A novelty in this plan was the concept of territorial integrity and connectivity among the constituent units (Nešković, 2017: 199).

³⁶ This agreement established the Muslim-Croat Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FBiH), a federal state comprising 10 cantons as its federal units. Three of these cantons have a Croat majority, five have a Bosniak majority, and two have a mixed ethnic composition of Croat and Bosniak.

³⁷ The Serbs accepted the constitutional component of this plan but rejected the territory it assigned for Republika Srpska. It envisaged a union (alliance) with mixed confederal and federal elements (Nešković, 2017: 206-207).

By emphasizing religious affiliation, it will become evident over time that it will be decisive in determining the direction of national identity development, as religious communities lived intermingled and were therefore oriented towards different cultural, civilizational, and spiritual sources (Hadžibegović & Kamberović, 1997: 99). “The key period for the consolidation of national identities began in the mid-19th century (or more precisely, from the early 1860s) and ended with the conclusion of the Eastern Crisis in 1878” (Radušić, 2009: 6). It is believed in science that at the time of the establishment of Austro-Hungarian rule in Bosnia and Herzegovina, national consciousness among its religious groups/peoples was not at a high level, but according to Mesić (2006: 291), the process of forming Serbian national consciousness among the Orthodox population in Bosnia and Herzegovina took precedence over others and was considered complete. The development of Croatian national consciousness among Bosnian and Herzegovinian Catholics lagged due to the oscillation between multi-religious Bosniakism – *bošnjaštvo* (partly supported by the Franciscans) and broader Yugoslavism, as well as previously existing Illyrism (Radušić, 2009: 5). However, in terms of the process of “ethnonomination” (Kržišnik-Bukić, 2003: 297-302) in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the greatest controversy at the turn of the 19th to the 20th century was the collective identification among Bosnian Muslims. European-educated Muslims, under the influence of Serbian or Croatian propaganda, were inclined to accept the Serbian or Croatian national idea (in the political sense) (Mesić, 2006: 291). Regardless of such propaganda pressure, Muslim Bosniaks will increasingly accept their a-nationality, a fact partly due to a more categorical refusal to embrace the Serbian or Croatian national idea, which implicitly indicates the crystallization of a separate Muslim-Bosniak national identity (Juzbašić, 1999: 66). Additionally, “we can also point to the fact that during the 19th century, Bosniak identity was created as a kind of antipode and reaction to the dominant Ottoman one, which was especially evident in the numerous efforts to ensure the status of Bosnia’s autonomy within this Empire” (Imamović, 1997: 333). As for the Austro-Hungarian period of Bosnia’s historical development, the original plan of the Empire and its governor for this ‘crown land’, Benjamin von Kállay, was “creating a regional, supra-confessional Bosniak identity based on the common language failed, and eventually gave way to the creation of the Bosniak nation in a narrower sense (based on religion, focusing on the Muslim Slavs of the region)” (Demeter & Bottlik, 2021: 41). The idea for supra-confessional Bosniak identity was rejected with the greatest indignation by the conservative Muslim beys, as well as the citizenry (Mesić, 2006: 291).

This historical development of Bosnia and Herzegovina will result in the country being well-placed in the category of “plural societies”, i.e. divided societies characterized by cultural diversity, and whose cultural parts aspire to organize themselves into cohesive political entities (Rezza & Mirković, 2019/2020: 1). The ultimate goal that will be set in the complex Dayton system is to incorporate such ethnic and cultural diversity into every aspect of the political structure (O. Bell, 2018: 20), by forcing the concept of “constituent peoples”. Bosnian-Herzegovinian society, as summarized in this chapter, was nationally divided even before 1990, and after the war, all the markers of a segmented society, which are well described in the works of Arend Lijphart (1992, 1998, 2003, 2004), only intensified. Therefore, with the DPA, the political and territorial organization of the state had to be aligned with the nature of society, not because someone wanted it to be, but simply because it could not function otherwise (Marković, 2015: 110).

3 THE CONSTITUTIVENESS OF THE CONSTITUENT PEOPLES IN DAYTON BIH

During the collapse of the former communist totalitarian regimes, a byproduct that emerged in several countries was the outbreak of ethnic nationalism. It was considered the main obstacle to a true democratization of countries in transition. International state-builders institutionalized it in the post-conflict remodelling of Bosnia and Herzegovina. This is most explicitly seen in the Preamble to the Constitution of BiH, but it was also reinforced in several other places in the normative part, which created a presumption favouring the three predominant ethnic groups to the detriment of the individual, i.e., the citizen. The Preamble to the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina defines Bosniaks, Serbs, and Croats as “constituent peoples,” while “others” and “citizens” are mentioned *en passant*. Hence, it is more than evident that individual rights are mistakenly (!?) granted to the three ethnic groups, and not to the citizens. Therefore, the concept of “constituent peoples” is considered to violate the ECHR, which protects the individual, not social, religious, or ethnic groups as such. The Dayton Constitution prioritizes collective rights over individual rights.³⁸ Additionally, it creates an assumption of power-sharing between the three constituent peoples, supporting and maintaining strong discrimination against non-constituent peoples (the others, the citizens) (Seizović, 2007: 2). However, formally, the constitutional framework stipulates that “the constituent peoples exercise sovereignty together with the citizens and other peoples” (Sahadžić, 2011: 30). Therefore, the contemporary political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina can be described as “a classical example of the application of a radical concept of multicultural politics (which, in truth, is gradually evolving) and a predominantly collectivist representation of constituent peoples and national minorities with a varying degree of provided rights” (Banović, 2016: 2).

The idea of constitutiveness is particularly complex and intricate when multiple constitutive, and thus sovereign, political communities exist and operate within a single legal and political order, creating a common internal framework in which general and special, common, and individual interests are addressed, positioned, and balanced. Additionally, the principle of constitutiveness reaffirms the idea of equality, which is extremely important in multinational states such as Bosnia and Herzegovina (Jašarević, 2023: 14).

For Kasim Trnka (2006: 175), the reason for this approach to materializing constitutiveness in the Bosnian-Herzegovinian Constitution is that no nation has a majority of more than half, and additionally, the emphasis is placed on its traditional multi-national composition. In this way, a combination of civic and national principles was achieved. According to the same author (Trnka, 2000: 50), in the etymological sense, the word “constitutive” originates from the Latin language, which as a verb (*constituo*) means to set up, to regulate, to establish, and as a noun (*constitutio*) means: internal structure, regulation, constitution, law.

However, it should be emphasized that the science of comparative constitutional law is not overly preoccupied with the concept of “constituent peoples”, for the simple reason that in established Western democracies, as well as other countries around the world, one nation or people has always been dominant by definition. For this reason, there

³⁸ For a certain group of authors, this is too reminiscent of the legacy of the millet system of the Ottoman Empire, „which recognised rights of communities, unlike the notion of citizenship that is based on individual rights“ (Koksal 2008: 1503).

are a small number of scientific and professional papers that touch on this issue (Sahadžić, 2011: 33).

In the given Bosnian-Herzegovinian context, but not only, “for a people to be constitutive, it must have the quality of an indigenous people.... From the fact of constitutiveness, the concept of equality of peoples is derived, that is, constituent peoples are equal in all rights and obligations” (Kuzmanović, 1997: 53). Therefore, it is natural and historical for people to have an aspiration to create their own state based on their autochthonous nature. Autochthonousness is a historical attribute and marker of every people, which exists in a certain natural space for a relatively long historical period, after which the respective area becomes recognizable by that people (Nešković, 2017: 43). The same author, referring to the example of Bosnia and Herzegovina, notes that it is a country on whose territory several indigenous peoples reside who strive to express themselves within the framework of the state in question. Croats, Serbs, and Bosniaks are indigenous ethnic nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina that emerged from ethnic-religious communities. Based on such autochthonousness and sovereignty, they are, by definition, constitutive and state-forming subjects of BiH. For them, Bosnia and Herzegovina is their home state, because in it the Serbian and Croatian nations are autochthonous and sovereign. In the opposite case, if Serbia and Croatia were declared the home states of Bosnian Serbs and Croats, then these two nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina would be reduced to national minorities and would lose their statehood. The autochthonous and sovereign status in BiH, with a parallel status of motherhood in another state, is unsustainable, because one excludes the other (Ibid., 421). Additionally, the autochthonous nature of a people may remain a historical fact without having any political or state consequences. Still, it may be a generator of its sovereignty and statehood with lasting political and state consequences (Ibid., 45).

Therefore, introducing the concept of “constituent peoples” into the Dayton constitutional and legal framework proved to be a *conditio sine qua non* because there are three autochthonous ethnic communities in the territory of BiH, which have the inalienable right to form and regulate its statehood, through the affirmation of the principle of equality. For this purpose, they need to be sovereign because their statehood stems from their sovereignty and autochthonism. “Constitutiveness as a political-legal concept and as a continuous process in the functioning of the political system is a derived category of popular sovereignty and only in this way does it have a democratic character” (Nešković, 2006: 165). The phrase “constituent peoples” as “a constitutional category, was first incorporated into the constitutional system of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina by the Washington Agreement in 1994. With the Dayton Peace Agreement, signed a year later, the concept of constitutiveness acquired the character of a constitutionally protected value on the territory of the entire Bosnia and Herzegovina” (Begić, 2011: 410). On the other hand, this phrase “is not used in the sense of people (*populous*) as the sum of all citizens who are in a civil relationship with Bosnia and Herzegovina and who constitute its political people, but is used in the sense of a separate ethnic identity” (Efendić, 2018: 80). Additionally, “The Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina does not define the term *constituent people*, rather, its definition is derived from the listing of groups that belong to constituent peoples, as well as the special collective rights these groups have” (Banović, 2016: 7). However, it should be emphasized that until the adoption of the Decision (no. U 5/98 – III) of the Constitutional Court of BiH in 2000, Serbs were the only constituent people in the Republika Srpska, and Bosniaks and Croats in the FBiH. With the Decision since then “the principle of collective equality of constituent peoples implies equal

collective rights, for all three groups, that are not territorially restricted, but relevant in both entities in equal ways regardless of whether the people in question represent a *de facto* minority or majority within an entity” (Ibid., 7-8).

It is essential to note that the term “constituent peoples” is not unfamiliar to the political science and practice of the former Yugoslavia. Still, in the constitutional development of the Yugoslav Federation, as well as Bosnia and Herzegovina as its constituent republic, it was not used as a constitutional category³⁹ (Trnka, 2006: 177). Due to this simple fact, the term “constituent peoples” can be considered a relatively new concept in constitutional and political theory and practice. In support of this thesis is the fact that it will be present in “Opinion 2 of the Arbitration Commission of the European Community, and the same term was used in the peace plans for Bosnia and Herzegovina (Cutileiro plan,⁴⁰ Vance-Owen plan,⁴¹ Owen-Stoltenberg plan,⁴² Contact Group plan)” (Sahadžić, 2011: 34).

The doyen of Bosnian-Herzegovinian constitutional law, academic Kasim Trnka, has offered the most comprehensive and fundamental definition of the idea of “constituent

³⁹ For example, at the first session of the Anti-fascist Council for the National Liberation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (ZAVNOBiH) in Mrkonjić Grad on 25 and 26 November 1943, decisions were made to restore the statehood of Bosnia and Herzegovina. A Resolution was adopted that reflects the common life of citizens regardless of differences in ethnic, religious, and any other respects. It states: „Today, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina, through their sole political representation, the Anti-fascist Council for the National Liberation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, want their country, which is neither Serbian, nor Croatian, nor Muslim, but Serbian, Muslim, and Croatian, to be a free and fraternal Bosnia and Herzegovina in which equity will be ensured for all Serbs, Muslims, and Croats. The peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina will participate equally with our other peoples in the construction of a People’s Democratic Federal Yugoslavia“ (quoted in Trnka, 2000: 17). At the second session of the ZAVNOH BiH, held in Sanski Most from June 30 to July 2, 1944, special emphasis was placed on „the equality of Serbs, Croats, and Muslims of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which is their common and indivisible homeland“ (quoted in Efendić, 2018: 63). From these two passages, it can be seen that although in these constituent documents that constituted BiH in 1943 as a federal state of Yugoslavia, the term “constituent peoples” is not used anywhere, however, as Kamberović notes (2013: 14-15), here „in fact all the important elements of its content and meaning are given“. In July 1990, the socialist leadership of Bosnia and Herzegovina passed an amendment to the Constitution that defined Bosnia and Herzegovina as „a democratic sovereign state of equal citizens, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina – Muslims, Serbs and Croats, and members of other peoples and nationalities living in that country“. Amendment LX to the Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina was adopted at a session of the Assembly on 31 July 1990. See: Official Gazette of the SR BiH (Sarajevo), 32 (1991). This amendment disrupts the democratic balance of the national and civic by separating sovereignty from the people and tying this concept to the state. According to Nešković (2017: 157), such a balance was guaranteed by the 1974 Constitution of the SR BiH, which states that the SR BiH is a „socialist democratic state... of the working people and citizens, the peoples of Bosnia and Herzegovina – Muslims, Serbs and Croats“ (Article 1), but also in Article 3 it is emphasized that in the SR BiH „the equality of peoples and nationalities is guaranteed“.

⁴⁰ Here „the concept of constitutiveness is related to the constituent territorial units“ (Efendić, 2018: 65).

⁴¹ „The plan accepts the category of ‘three constituent peoples’ and the category of members of the ‘other’ peoples“ (Efendić, 2018: 66).

⁴² „This plan uses the term ‘constituent republic’ which was supposed to mean territorialization for each constituent people, i.e. the creation of ethnically pure territories“ (Efendić, 2018: 66).

peoples” in the context of BiH constitutionalism: “The constitutiveness of peoples is a collective right narrower than sovereignty, but broader than the individual right to national identity. Constitutiveness does not entail the right to self-determination or the right to secession. No people exercises its constitutiveness independently of other peoples who have the same rights. Constitutiveness implies the mutual right of all three peoples to determine the constitutional order (together with citizens and others) and to use all mechanisms for the realization and protection of national equality” (Trnka, 2006: 178).

However, in Bosnian-Herzegovinian scientific thought, some authors take more controversial positions regarding the constitutiveness of the three peoples. So, Omer Ibrahimagić (1995) argues that “historically, there is no scientific basis for Bosniaks, Serbs and Croats to declare themselves constitutive nations. From a historical point of view, those three nations did not constitute Bosnia and Herzegovina as a country, but Bosnia as a thousand-year-old political space, on which an internationally recognized state of the same name existed for several centuries, and constituted the three existing nations today (...). The theory of constitutive nations in Bosnia and Herzegovina is directly related to the destruction of Bosnia and Herzegovina as a sovereign state with a unique territory”. Efendić (2018: 71) criticizes Ibrahimagić’s manipulativeness, noting that he replaces the original term “constituent peoples” in the Dayton Constitution with “constitutive nations”. Constituent peoples cannot be equated with the term ‘nation’, because it is synonymous with the state.

Hence, it can be concluded that the concept of constitutiveness in BiH seriously differs from the theoretical meaning of this term, due to the non-standardized use of the terms people and nation. From the entire discussion presented in this chapter, it can be concluded that the principle of the constitutiveness of peoples is not compatible with international democratic standards (Jašarević, 2023: 68, 71), which is why it has caused certain repercussions in the development of Bosnia and Herzegovina in the past three decades.

4 THE NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE IMPLICATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF CONSTITUENT PEOPLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF POST-DAYTON BIH

From the perspective of the constitutional and legal system of BiH, as well as the current situation in the country, the issue of the “constituent peoples” emerges as problematic in two domains: human rights and fundamental freedoms, and in the view of the organization and structure of government (Begić, 1997: 9). “The complexity of the constitutional architecture of Bosnia and Herzegovina based on the Dayton Peace Agreement has contributed to the continuity of the socio-political dominance of ethnic nationalism (...) based on the supremacy of collective rights, and consequently on proportional representation of the constituent peoples as a fundamental principle of the political decision-making process” (Dedić, 2015: 203-204). All the institutions inaugurated in the DPA for the post-conflict reorganization of the country were, to a large extent, created from a too primordialist understanding of ethnicity and its institutionalization within the system.⁴³ The concept of ethnicity is so entwined with the Dayton regime that it

⁴³ The political representation of the constituent peoples is almost perfectly reflected by the composition of the House of Peoples (the second chamber of the Parliamentary Assembly – HP PABiH) and the House of Representatives: the first is composed of five Bosniaks and the same number of Croats from the Federation of BiH and five Serbs from the Republika Srpska, while a

is practically impossible to be a Bosnian – a citizen of BiH simply. This is primarily due to the effectively established hierarchy, where the three constituent peoples have priority in terms of political rights, while others (the various ethnic and national minorities, as well as ethnically undetermined citizens) are placed in the background (Mujanović, 2020: 6). Such an interaction between the division of the population into three constituent peoples and the exercise of veto powers transformed, *de facto*, a system based on equal representation of ethnic groups into a system detrimental to the rights of ‘others’ (Marko, 1996). As Asim Mujkić (2008: 20) suggests, “from the perspective of democratic consolidation, this constitutional order replaces the ideal of the polis with that of the Ethnopolis. The subversive mechanism of Ethnopolitics consists in the practice of *presenting ethnos as demos*, where *ethnos* acts like *demos*”.

minimum number of 4 representatives of one constituent people need to be represented in the House of Representatives. Additionally, there is also the Presidency (collective head of state) made up of three members, with a Bosniak and a Croat from the FBiH and a Serb from the RS. It follows from this that only persons who declare themselves to belong to the constituent peoples have the right to run for the House of Peoples and the Presidency. In other words, these institutions only include people from the three ethnic groups, effectively excluding and discriminating against the group “other” (Alicino, 2016: 149-150). This was pointed out by the ECtHR in the well-known case *Sejdić and Finci (of Roma and Jewish origin) vs. BiH*. However, these two institutions also discriminate against members of the three constituent peoples, because for their election, in addition to the ethnic criterion, the entity criterion has been introduced. So Serbs from the FBiH, or Bosniaks or Croats from the RS cannot be chosen for these positions. This is indicated by the judgment of the ECtHR in the case of *Pilav vs. BiH*. There is also a third group of discriminated citizens, given this issue, as was highlighted in the case of *Zornić vs. BiH* before the ECtHR, where the citizen in question refuses to declare herself either as a member of the three constituent peoples, nor as a national minority, but simply as a citizen of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Efendić, 2018: 86-87). However, the ECtHR ruled in a different direction in 2025 in the case of *Kovačević vs. BiH*. Unlike previous cases that indicated a violation of the passive right to vote (i.e., the right to be elected), this complaint stated a violation of the active right to vote. Due to the combination of territorial and ethnic criteria for election to the HP PABiH and the Presidency, the applicant complained that, as a member of the “others”, he could not vote for candidates of his own choice. It should be emphasized that the initial judgment found a violation of Article 1 of Protocol No. 12 to the ECHR. However, two of the three BiH agents before the ECtHR (from among the Serb and Croat people) appealed to the Grand Chamber of the ECtHR, which overturned the initial verdict. The Republic of Croatia and the Office of the High Representative for Bosnia and Herzegovina were actively involved in overturning the verdict. For the representative of Croatia before the ECtHR, the applicant’s request constitutes an ‘*actio popularis*’ because his Democratic Front party aims to reconstruct the constitutional framework of BiH and eliminate the notion of “constituent peoples” in the BiH electoral system, rather than protecting human rights. The Bosnian Croat agent before the ECtHR also proved that Kovačević had previously declared himself a Croat. Additionally, it turned out that he also holds Croatian citizenship, which was another argument for Croatia’s involvement in the entire case. It was the Croatian representative before the ECtHR who warned that the possible confirmation of the verdict would have far-reaching consequences for other consociational democracies in Europe (such as Belgium and Switzerland) as well as for the positive obligations of all CoE member states in terms of ensuring active voting rights. The fall of the verdict in the second instance was greeted with enthusiasm by some Serbian and Croatian politicians in BiH, according to whom the imposed narrative of BiH as a civil state had suffered a defeat, and that the court had returned BiH to where it should be – to an internal mutual agreement of the constituent peoples. The concern of the Croatian and Serbian political elites regarding this case was the fact that, unlike previous rulings that pointed to ethnic discrimination, the initial ruling in this case also spoke of discrimination based on territoriality.

However, the BiH constitution manages to some extent to maneuver between formal provisions for non-discrimination between the different ethnic groups in the country on the one hand, and the introduction of a mechanism for the sharing of power between the three constituent peoples, in response to their desire to have a strong stake in the state (Keil, 2021: 338). But consociational arrangements, such as Dayton undoubtedly is, often sacrifice the human rights of certain groups by favoring others (the constituent peoples in this case), precisely through this type of constitutional engineering (O. Bell, 2018: 19). Such a form of “ethnic sovereignty” (Yee, 1996: 187), at the state and parliamentary level, in fact established a “participatory ethnocracy” (Šarčević, 2010: 42) between three dominant ethnic groups or the so-called “constituent peoples” (Bosniaks, Croats and Serbs).

But this does not necessarily have a negative connotation *per se*. In the academic literature, Bosnia is often portrayed as a version of Europe in a microcosm, and the consociational arrangements that the International Community imposed on it for sharing power between representatives of the three main ethnic groups in Bosnia are depicted as similar to the historical experience of the EU itself (including some of its founding member states, such as Belgium, for example) (Cooley, 2011: 3). The international intervention in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the Dayton Peace Agreement, thirty years ago, “had no ambitions of conciliation among the different ethnic and religious groups (...) The power-sharing mechanism, the consociational democracy as well as the mechanisms of quotas were not created to reconcile ethnos and demos, but rather to the restoration of peace after a civil war...” (Piergigli, 2016: 126). So although Dayton is destined for criticism, it “remains a best practice in the international experience of conflict resolution and for reconstruction of national identity through institution building and governance” (Woelk, 2016: 21). The DPA created an assumption of a ‘negative peace’ that segregates, but also mutually controls; that generates ethnic divisions and tensions, to later moderate them. Even the most frenetic supporters of Lijphart’s model of consociational democracy admit that the partial failure of the International Community in Bosnia and Herzegovina is because, when drafting the DPA, it favoured the so-called “corporate” rather than “liberal” consociativism (McGarry & Moore, 2005: 87; McGarry et al., 2008: 61-62). With the deep imprint of ethnicity in Bosnian-Herzegovinian institutions, instead of liberal, procedural democracy was installed among the political representatives – or rather, the ruling oligarchies – of the three ethnic groups (Mujkić, 2007: 112). Such procedural democracy, in which ethnicity plays an important role, was actually experienced in the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina as a “correction” of liberal democracy based on individual rights, due to the evident institutional recognition of the three ethnic groups as a necessity (Woelk, 2016: 30).

But, thirty years after Dayton, a certain group of authors think that such an example of an extreme combination of power-sharing and “ethnic federalism”, which cements the territorial consolidation of ethnicity, needs “correction”, but in the opposite direction – through building a sustainable multinational system, strengthening the civil and liberal component, whereby guarantees for groups cannot completely override individual human rights. Without such a “civic” counterbalance, the system will inevitably continue to degenerate into an “ethnic democracy” (Ibid., 49). In this context, there are also opposing views. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, a civic nation as a state-forming entity has never existed, nor has a people understood as a demos, which would have founded such a civic nation. Hence, it is more realistic to build upon, rather than eliminate, the ethnic

foundations, through the acceptance of universal civic European values by all three ethnic nations, to build a common civic identity that would not nullify their current ethnic identity (Nešković, 2017: 328).

CONCLUSION

Thirty years after the civil war, the DPA maintained peace in Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, “there is a strong sense of dissatisfaction with the internal structure, as established in Dayton” (Jović, 2016: 33). Today, the Dayton Arrangement is associated less with its peace dimension and much more with the dysfunction it produced. Partly this is because Dayton was more of a truce than an agreement (Hamilton, 2020: 1).

From the discussion presented above, it can be noted that this conclusion is partly borne out by the concept of “constituent peoples”, which was introduced with the General Framework Agreement for Peace, and which was “problematic for the consolidation of the country, especially due to the tense relations between the three major ethnic groups after the war in 1995” (Džihić, 2016). “Therefore, the principle of a purely collectivist representation and the predominance of collective rights in the political system of Bosnia and Herzegovina have influenced the disruption of a citizen principle taken as an abstract category” (Banović, 2016: 3).

That is why in science, there are two antagonistic views on Dayton’s achievements. The first, affirmative, places emphasis on bringing the war to an end, creating the foundations for internal integration, and building democratic institutions, which were supposed to consolidate peace and pave the way for European integration. The second, critical, considered that the Agreement divided Bosnia and Herzegovina on an ethnic basis, hypostatizing the ethnic principle, including through the idea of “constituent peoples” and their impregnation in the internal structure and functioning of the state, which became dysfunctional, non-independent, expensive and unsustainable, creating assumptions for a “frozen conflict” (Simić, 2016: 81). The BiH Constitution obstructs the creation of a plural civic identity, hypostasizes the collective political mentality. Spiritual usurpation has moved into the realm of identity (Hadžić, 2021: 67-85), thus, BiH, as the most critical multiethnic discourse in the Region, is in constant crisis due to ethnopolitical conflicts (Hadžić, 2022: 145).

Dayton should not be glorified merely as an end to the civil war, but rather recognized as a dangerous concept that emanates many of the same policies that destroyed the Yugoslav federation, which Dayton merely replaced (Mujanović, 2020: 1). To overcome its shortcomings, which are partly produced by the way in which the concept of “constituent peoples” is elaborated, a dialogue is needed between all stakeholders toward a more comprehensive constitutional reform. Some authors, a few years ago, such as Simić (2016: 84), suggested that the country’s European integration path is the best framework in which such reform should take place. Through this “Brussels Avenue”, BiH would gain a foundation similar to that of the EU member states today, which are internally integrated, and have developed institutions, which are synonymous with a functional state. In this way, the shortcomings of the DPA would be corrected, and the integration process itself and the implementation of a clearly defined reform agenda would be its positive upgrade.

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